

Energy-Space Statistical Features of the Klein-Gordon Equation

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In a previous note (1), we argued that maximization of Shannon's entropy $-P(x)\ln(P(x))$ subject to the periodic (complex) constraint $i p x P(x)$ yields the free particle two-dimensional probability $\exp(ipx)$. Similarly one may obtain $\exp(-iEt)$ (with a minus associated with E to allow for $-Et+px$ to remain invariant under $t \rightarrow t+\text{constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x+\text{constant}/p$), also for a free particle. We argued that multiplying the two together $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ yields a phase which should be invariant when seen from frames moving at constant average velocity $v=x/t$. This means that not only $-Et+px$, but $-EE+pp=c^2$ ($c=1$) is a Lorentz invariant. The latter, however, represents conservation of energy for no potential. We argue that conservation of energy for a free particle is linked to both the maximization of Shannon's entropy for both E and p , i.e. it is an equilibrium in both time and space. We have argued before that in the presence of a potential $V(x)$, one may replace E with $E-V(x)$ in the Klein-Gordon equation. Here we wish to examine the statistical features of this situation in more detail.

Finally, we note that the third statistical feature is present, associated with the absorption or emission of a photon. The photon wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is subject to both E and p maximization of Shannon's entropy and it is associated with an equilibrium E_1 or E_2 energy level of say an electron in an atom. The difference is that this absorption or emission seems to occur stochastically without being directly linked to the momentum impulse hits between the electron and $V(x)$. In describing photon emission/absorption, one may maximize Shannon's entropy using only conservation of energy, i.e. use the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor. The x and t notion of maximum entropy are still present as the photon wavefunction is $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. The photon momentum, however, is conserved with the total momentum of the atom and not the impulse hits of the electron with $V(x)$. The two stochastic features occur together.

Maximization of Shannon's Entropy

In (1), we argued that maximization of Shannon's entropy $-P(e)\ln(P(e))$ subject to a constraint $e P(e)$ yields an equation: $1+P(e) = b e$ (b =Lagrange multiplier). One may take the gradient d/de of this equation to find how $P(e)$ changes in e . In other words, a balance equation is obtained which shows how probability changes i.e.

$$dP/de = b \quad ((1))$$

For a coin or die, the constraint is b , so $db/di = 0$ and $dP/di=0$ i.e. there is no probability flow. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, it is $((1))$. We suggested in (1), however, that for a free particle with momentum p , one may create a periodic boundary condition i.e. maximize

$$-P(x)\ln(P(x)) + i p x P(x) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{This yields:} \quad dP/dx = p P(x) \quad ((2b))$$

In other words, p is an impulse and probability seems to balance it like pressure and force in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas: $dP(x)/dx T = -dV/dx P(x)$ where $-1/T$ is the Lagrange multiplier and T , temperature.

((2a)) yields $P(x) = \exp(ipx)$. ((3)) Similarly, one may consider $P(t)$ and obtain $\exp(-iEt)$ ((3b)). We deliberately associate a minus sign with E so that for the product $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, $t \rightarrow t + \text{constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \text{constant}/p$ leave the exponent unchanged.

This approach treats t and x as independent but at the same time one has, on average,

$$x/t = v = \text{constant} \quad ((4))$$

Classically, p is associated with impulse and so there is a physical resistance as a particle moves according to the gradient of maximum entropy. We argue there is also the classical notion of inertia which represents resistance. Inertia is associated with rest mass, but a moving mass still contains this inertia as well as enhancements due to motion. We argue that $\exp(-iEt)$ represents a resistance due to enhanced inertia. As a result, for a free particle, maximization of entropy, followed by a gradient, yields balance equations in x and t due to different kinds of resistance. At this point, E and p are not linked, but are physically associated with resistances which, in turn, are linked with maximization of entropy, i.e. stochasticity.

To link E and p , one may note that:

$$P(x)P(t) = \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((5))$$

As we have suggested before, if one wishes the argument to be invariant as seen from frames moving with an average velocity v , the $-Et+px$ must be an invariant (Lorentz invariant). This condition then also holds for:

$$-EE + pp = m^2 c^2 \quad ((6)) \quad \text{i.e. one has an } E, p \text{ relationship}$$

((6)) is called conservation of energy, but we argue it is associated with two statistical resistance quantities E and p to ensure that a product probability is invariant. Conservation of energy is a statistical statement in terms of both E and p i.e. in t and x because both E and p represent resistances in balance equations which follow from maximizing Shannon's entropy due to periodic constraints.

We also note that in the three-dimensional Klein-Gordon equation $-EE + p \cdot p = m^2 c^2$ ($c=1$), there is an invariance, i.e. the p vector may point in any direction and still represent the same E . Thus one may have impulse hits which change the direction of p , but not its magnitude, and retain the value of E .

The Case of a Potential $V(x)$

We next consider a potential $V(x)$. In previous notes, we replaced E with $E-V(x)$ in the Klein-Gordon equation and used an average for pp i.e.

$$\langle pp \rangle = \frac{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) p^2}{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)} \quad ((7))$$

We wish to examine this in more detail. $\exp(ipx)$ contains momentum which may change subject to impulse hits. These impulse hits may exist in space. Consider maximizing entropy for p_1+p_2 , because momenta add:

$$\text{Maximize } -P(x) \ln(P(x) + i(p_1+p_2) x P(x)) \quad ((8a))$$

$$\text{Next consider maximizing: } -P_1(x) \ln(P_1(x)) + i p_1 x P_1(x) \text{ and } -P_2 \ln(P_2) + i p_2 x P_2 \quad ((8b))$$

Adding the two equations of ((8b)) with the first multiplied by P_2 and the second by P_1 yields: ((8a)).

$$\text{Thus } P_1(x)P_2(x)=P(x) \quad ((8c))$$

In other words, an interaction involving p_1 and p_2 , subject to maximization of Shannon's entropy, is equivalent to the separate maximization for p_1 and p_2 . This suggests the form $\exp(ipx)$, which applies to a free quantum particle, should also be the form for a system which may interact with $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. something we call $V(x)$ because it has a distribution in space. Then it seems one is justified in writing:

$$V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((9))$$

At this point, we have made no statement about energy, but a free particle which receives an impulse hit and changes from p_1 to p_2 changes its energy, and hence its resistance in time. As a result, it seems one may consider an ensemble $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ interacting with a $V(x)$ i.e.

$$W(x)V(x) \quad ((10))$$

((10)) represents impulse hits which are associated with energy, but at the same time, these impulse hits create an average resistance in time (due to kinetic energy):

$$\text{Average kinetic energy} = \frac{\sum_p a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx)}{W(x)} \quad ((11))$$

In other words, the function $V(x)$ imparts impulses controlled by the maximization of Shannon's entropy $\exp(ipx)$, but this in turn creates a kinetic energy average in space as well as a potential energy distribution because work is done during impulse hits as p_1 changes into p_2 . We have argued that a relationship between p (impulse hits) and E (energy) (i.e. conservation of energy) is due to the overall invariance of the phase of probability, i.e. is a statistical consequence. If one wishes the system associated with ((10)) and ((11)) to represent one value of resistance in time, i.e. constant E , then ((10)) and ((11)) must balance. We note that the $W(x)$ in ((10)) follows from multiplying ((11)) by $W(x)$. Thus we suggest that:

$$W(x) * \text{Average kinetic energy} + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((12))$$

This leads to a single resistance in time value E for all x , i.e. a quantum bound state for the Klein-Gordon equation. The time-independent Schrodinger equation may be obtained from the Klein-Gordon one in the nonrelativistic limit, as is often done in the literature. Thus a bound state with constant E is associated with a specific statistical balance equation in time.

Photon Absorption/Emission

We have argued above that maximization of Shannon's entropy with periodic constraints leads to resistance balance equations in time and space associated with $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. Next, we consider the absorption or emission of a photon. A photon which is absorbed or emitted conserves momentum and energy (with the atom) and so one expects the arguments of ((8a)), ((8b)), ((8c)) to hold for both E and t . They do as the photon is described by $\exp(-iEt)$. There is also an $\exp(ip_1 x)$ function associated with p_1 , the overall momentum of the atom. This is different from the impulse hits of the electron with $V(x)$ which control the bound state.

There is, however, an additional statistical consideration i.e. an additional stochasticity beyond the maximization of Shannon's entropy associated with energy and momentum conservation, namely that stochasticity of absorption or emission. Given that E and p are conserved in an interaction between an atom and photon, that still does not indicate when and how the photon is absorbed or emitted. The event itself of absorption or emission thus seems to be stochastic and separate from E and p conservation. This event is not associated with resistance in time and space as these are already incorporated in $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ for the photon and $\exp(-iEnt)$ for the atom. Furthermore the electron forms a bound state with $V(x)$ through the $\exp(ipx)\exp(iix)$ interactions and the sum of average kinetic energy and potential yielding a constant E . The absorption/emission of a photon does not change these features it just changes the overall energy associated with them. Thus, it appears as a stochastic event signaling a change between one E_n and another, where E_n is the bound state energy of the electron.

. This situation seems to be very similar to the two body collisions which occur in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. Even though momentum is conserved for the atom as a whole and energy as a whole, it is the energy jump of the electron which is of concern, without considerations of its resistance in time. We suggest that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution (associated with maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to an average energy constraint for the electron) describes the situation of atoms with two levels (ground and excited) interacting with photons i.e.

$$\exp(-E_n/T) \quad ((13)) \text{ describes the probability for an electron to be energy state } E_n$$

It seems one has to distinguish between maximization of entropy in time and space and that associated with stochastic interactions where the stochasticity is in the event itself, like tossing a coin or die. $\exp(ipx)$ is used when there are direct impulse hits to the electron. The absorption or emission of a photon, however, is not seen in this way, rather the entire E_n changes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to a constraint, followed by a gradient of the variable of probability leads to a balance type equation. In the case of time or space x , one may introduce periodic boundary conditions - $i t E P(t)$ or $i p x P(x)$ to obtain $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$. The balance equations seem to be linked with p , impulse, or E (related to enhanced inertia). Thus both are associated with a resistance, one in time, the other in space. We argue that for such constraints, $P((p_1+p_2)x) = P(p_1x)P(p_2x)$ which gives insight into the interactions which occur, i.e. between $V(x)$ (potential) and $W(x) = \sum_a(p) \exp(ipx)$. We argue that the Klein-Gordon equation, which links E and p , is directly linked to probability because the argument of $P(x)P(t) = \exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is invariant suggesting $-EE+pp$ is also invariant i.e. equal to $m^2 c^2$ ($c=1$). Thus conservation of energy is associated with $\exp(-iEt)$, i.e. with the resistance of inertia, enhanced by motion, in time.

It seems, however, that there is another stochastic process which is not associated with a periodic (complex constraint). This is the one associated with the stochasticity of an event, i.e. the toss of coin or die. In a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, it is linked with two body collisions. For the quantum bound state, we suggest that a similar process is that of the absorption/emission of a photon. The photon has a wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, so the usual periodic probability associated with maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to periodic constraints is present, but there is a second source of stochasticity linked with an uncertainty of absorption or emission which gives rise to a Maxwell-Boltzmann type factor $\exp(-E_n/T)$ for a two-level electron-nucleus system.

In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ are used to describe a specific energy conserving interaction. For an electron, $\exp(ipx)$ is linked with impulse hits from a potential. This does not change if a photon is absorbed or emitted. From the photon point of view, when it is emitted, it gains momentum and energy through its interaction with the whole atom, hence $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is appropriate for the emitted photon because this describes its interaction. From the point of view of the electron, an emitted/absorbed photon simply changes E_n , not the form of the interactions which create the resonance bound state. Thus the photon is treated as a stochastic event from the point of view of the electron, and not as a direct interaction involving $\exp(ipx)$ for the photon and electron. Thus, both types of stochasticity, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and $\exp(-E_n/T)$, may be present in a problem.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Maximum Entropy Subject to a Constraint In Terms of a Gradient of Probability (preprint, zenodo, 2023)